
WHAT NOT TO DO WHEN CREATING A DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN (DMP)

**GEORGIA KOUTENTAKI^{1,2} **

Affiliations:

1. *Czech Technical University, Prague*
2. *University of Chemistry and Technology, Prague*
3. *National Library of Technology, Prague*

Contact the author: geokout.ds@gmail.com

The creation and execution of data management plans (DMP) is a tricky concept. It is crucial to understand what the DMP is, how to use it for your benefit, and what to avoid in order to have a transparent, ethical, and safe approach.

First things first, what is a Data Management Plan? A DMP is a document that explains extensively how the data management of a research project has been planned, what steps should be taken, and how this data management organization allows the research to become FAIR, support open science, and follow legal and ethical guidelines. A DMP is a living document. It contains information before the project (expectations and plans), then it is updated with current information, usually in the middle of the project, and lastly, the last version should contain the actual data management methods that were followed through the project.

Why should someone create a DMP? Except for being a mandatory part of some funder policies, a data management plan gives proper documentation on how the data was (or is to be) handled, where the data is, how it was collected, and how it can be harvested and reused. This way, it is ensured that research and data comply with national and international guidelines, and it is not lost and destroyed after a project is completed. That allows us to continue building on already accomplished research and finalize, improve, or adjust it. But more importantly, a DMP is a fundamental document for a research team since it gives all members the appropriate guidelines and policies, they all must follow during the project, from naming conventions to licensing. It ensures that the researchers and stakeholders are well-informed and have a guide to follow when in doubt. The data resulting in following the same rules that are stated in a DMP are more comprehensible, can be read and used in combination, and give a general image of what the research was about. That is why a DMP should always contain the truth.

But now, let's reach the main point: What should you NOT do when creating (and implementing) a DMP?

1. You should NOT wait until the deadline of sending the DMP. You should always and in all phases of the DMP circle have a draft DMP ready at least a month before the deadline. This way you can ensure

that your research colleagues/supervisors/stakeholders/etc., can double-check the information and you still have enough time for changes. Moreover, if you have a data steward consulting you on the DMP and you are not data steward yourself, you should give them enough time to review, suggest and correct your DMP. This process takes a minimum of 2 weeks for very small projects. For large projects it can take up to one month or more.

2. You should NOT create a DMP manually. You can, but it is not what is recommended. Many online services, free or otherwise, provide guidance on DMP creation, such as the DSW (Data Stewardship Wizard), FAIR Wizard, DMPonline and more. Such tools can help you navigate and create DMPs that are accessible by multiple members for example, some work on question-answer basis and allow you to see metrics of your DMP (how FAIR it is, and more). Such services also allow you to save your DMP in more than one format, not only as human-readable but also machine-actionable documents.
3. When in the “Before the Project” phase of the DMP cycle, you should NOT try to impress and make false promises. The information of the DMP is the same as when writing a project proposal, but it contains information for the data created or used within the project. What you write in the DMP is what is expected of you during the data management process of the project, and it is used as a guideline for checking and auditing your final (and actual) data management and manipulation practices. For example, if you write in your DMP that all data will be immediately available in a repository, you should not forget that promise and you should genuinely follow that rule for your data. So do not write a DMP promising that you will be having the most “open” and “FAIRest” DMP of the world. No, write what you really expect of this project data. Write the DMP with clear intent and promise only things you understand.
4. Do NOT avoid adding people/institutes/companies dealing with data on a DMP. When creating a DMP, you need to inform WHO is dealing with the data and in what way. And no, dealing with data is not only about creation, analysis, and curation. Dealing with data can simply be: I am the rightsholder of data, I am a stakeholder, I am a data auditor, I am a data steward, etc. Because you are creating the DMP, it does not mean you are the only contributor.
5. Do NOT forget to make a naming-convention for file and/or folder naming. File/folder naming is a common issue when it comes to research projects. Look from the classic jfdsf.doc to the impressive finalfinalfinalfinal234.txt. These are terrible examples of non-existent naming conventions. A naming convention can help you navigate through the project data, not only as an external viewer but also as part of the research team. When you need to analyze someone else’s data, or simply check them, a proper name can help you navigate and understand much easier what the data is. For example: YYYYMMDDofcreation_datatype_version is a clear naming convention. It does not apply to everything, but it is a good example. You can clearly see when the data set was created, what type of data it is (e.g. FT-IR spectra), and what version of the dataset you will be reading.
6. Do NOT skip making agreements for the rights of data! When creating a project proposal with multiple members, you should already have decided who (institute/PI/supervisor...) is the rightsholder of the data, who has the right to work with and share data, etc. If you skip this step, you risk the possibility of someone sharing the data without the consent of the rightsholder, which can even lead to legal battles. Make proper agreements and state them in your DMP!

7. Do NOT choose whatever license for your data records. When publishing your data, and if you followed step 6, you must have some specifications on what licenses the data can be published, and who decides that. Do not forget to double check with the rightsholder!
8. When in the “During the Project” and “After the Project” phases of a DMP, do NOT forget to include ALL already published and created data. The phases “during” and “after” are essential for checking if you follow what you mentioned in the “before” phase of your DMP. You can still make changes and explain why you did not follow specific steps. But at this stage you should already have enough information about what is being followed and what not, the size of your data and licensing options.
9. Do NOT write abbreviations (without explaining them). Researchers of specific fields might understand your abbreviations, but a DMP is not always read by such people of the same field. When in need of abbreviations, you should always explain them to avoid confusion. Example: API in some fields means Application Programming Interface, while in others it means Active Pharmaceutical Ingredients. By avoiding the long version of the abbreviation, you risk a highly possible confusion, based on who is reading your DMP and/or data.
10. Do NOT forget your metadata! By this point, you should understand that everything data-related you create and use in the project should be explained in a nice and comprehensive way. METADATA is basically all the information explained: what is this data, how it was created/used, who is the rightsholder, under what license can they be shared/used or changed if any, how can you repeat the experiment to see if you will get the same data, and more. Do NOT forget: contact information, legal issues such as licenses, methods of collection/analysis and equipment. These are the bare minimum metadata you MUST provide.
11. Do NOT be afraid. DMPs are considered, many times, dead-weight or difficult to create and follow. Do not allow yourself to be consumed by anxiety or fear. A DMP is a strong tool for you and your team, that can help you be a better scientist and support your research.
12. Do NOT forget to share and promote your data together with papers and results of your research. Data, presentations or images can create a big impact and will bring more attention to your research.
13. Do NOT think this is all... Even though it would be wonderful for all the information that could help you with the DMP was here, it is not possible to discuss all the details that go into DMP in general. Each project and DMP are a unique combination of the needs of the team, the regulations at national and international level, funders’ policies, institutional policies, budgetary restrictions and more. As such, they should be discussed in detail individually, and preferably with the help of a data steward.

All in all, you should not forget that a DMP is for your own assistance, and you should not be scared to create and implement it. Feel free to write to us if you wish to discuss DMPs and other relevant topics further.

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References:

1. Data Stewardship Course, Doc Enhance. <https://courses.docenhance.eu/>
2. Lushaj, B., & Hernandez Esponda, C. (2025, February 26). The DOs and DON'Ts of Data Management Plans. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14927848>